

Review Article

CRISPR-Cas9 as a Potential Cancer Therapy Agent: An Update

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ABSTRACT

Cancer is the second leading cause of death globally and remains a major economic and social burden. Although our understanding of cancer at the molecular level continues to improve, more effort is needed to develop new therapeutic tools and approaches exploiting these advances. Due to its high efficiency and accuracy, the CRISPR-Cas9 genome editing technique has recently emerged as a cancer treatment strategy. Among its many applications, CRISPR-Cas9 has shown an unprecedented clinical potential to discover novel targets for cancer therapy and to dissect chemical-genetic interactions, providing insight into how tumors respond to drug treatment. Moreover, CRISPR-Cas9 can be employed to rapidly engineer immune cells and oncolytic viruses for cancer immunotherapeutic applications. More importantly, the ability of CRISPR-Cas9 to accurately edit genes, not only in cell culture models and model organisms but also in humans, allows its use in therapeutic explorations. This review, important considerations for the use of CRISPR/Cas9 in therapeutic properties are discussed, along with major challenges that will need to be addressed before clinical examinations for a complex and polygenic disease such as cancer. This review aimed to explore the potential of the CRISPR-Cas9 genome editing technique as a cancer treatment strategy. Specifically, we will discuss how CRISPR-Cas9 can be used to discover novel targets for cancer therapy and to dissect chemical-genetic interactions.

1. Introduction

In most countries of the world, cancer contributes to early mortality¹. Cancer incidence worldwide will increase within the next 50 years due to changes in the population, including aging and population growth and differences in cancer rates in various places². Based on the latest incidence trends in the most frequently occurring types of cancer, the number of cancer cases will double by 2070, compared to 2020. Those increases will be greatest in countries with low Human Development Indexes (HDI) in low-resource settings. In contrast, the expected decrease in a national burden can be possible by increasing HDI levels³. Although molecular understanding of cancer is improving, new treatments are still needed to exploit discoveries.

In recent years, immunotherapy has significantly increased tumor responses with adverse reactions and reduced toxicity^{4,5}. Nevertheless, the development of drug

resistance and the high recurrence rate for most cancers call for innovative treatments⁶. Cancer drugs are often given multiple times, but this can lead to increased toxicity and costs, lowering the quality of patients' life. Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats (CRISPR) are a natural defense mechanism against exogenous plasmids and viruses⁷. The CRISPR/Cas system comprises six categories of CRISPR-associated (Cas) proteins, each with its unique functions. Type II systems, with Cas9 protein and single guide RNA (sgRNA), are famous for editing molecules⁸. The type II CRISPR/Cas9 system dominates genome editing today. There are two main classes of Cas protein, as categorized by their structural and functional differences. In class 1, multi-Cas proteins are used, while in class 2, a single large Cas protein is used; both types degrade foreign nucleic acids. Of these, two

main Cas proteins are of interest, namely Cas9 and Cas1-Cas2 complex⁹. The Cas1-Cas2 complex gathers DNA from the invading phage or virus to create a memory. The Cas9 protein is an effector protein guided by CRISPR RNA (crRNA) or RNA (gRNA). It can detect and destroy foreign RNA or DNA that matches the guide sequence, thereby preventing re-invasion by pathogens¹⁰.

On-site and real-time clinical monitoring has advanced significantly by combining biosensors with portable electronic devices. The CRISPR and RNA-guided nucleases (CrRNA-Cas enzymes) provide CRISPR/Cas biosensing science as a revolutionary technique for mobile and on-site healthcare diagnostics and monitoring^{11,12}. Among the various CRISPR/Cas systems, CRISPR/Cas13a and CRISPR/Cas12a hybrids are widely used in biosensor design since they can remove both target and non-target DNA¹³. The CRISPR/Cas-based biosensors are ideal for creating diagnostic ultra-sensitive point-of-care systems with enhanced response signals that are cost-effective, portable, reproducible, and highly durable¹⁴.

CRISPR-Cas9 offers the unique clinical ability to identify new molecules for treating cancer and analyze chemical-genetic reactions, revealing how drugs affect tumor growth¹⁵. Moreover, CRISPR-Cas9 can efficiently construct oncolytic viruses and immune cells for cancer immunotherapy. Furthermore, CRISPR-Cas9's ability to precisely modify genes in humans, cell culture models, and model organisms makes it useful as a therapeutic tool. The Cas9 can be directed to particular sites in a genome by a short RNA search string; DNA sequences within the endogenous genome can now be modified almost anywhere¹⁶. The Cas9-mediated genetic modification is quick and easy, allowing researchers to understand the structure of the genome in detail and determine causal links between biological phenotypes and genetic variants¹⁷. This review aimed to explore the potential of the CRISPR-Cas9 genome editing technique as a cancer treatment strategy, discussing its applications in discovering novel targets for cancer therapy, dissecting chemical-genetic interactions, engineering immune cells and oncolytic viruses for cancer immunotherapy, and editing genes in humans.

2. Advancement of gene editing with CRISPR-Cas9 technology

There have been several methods designed to enable effective gene editings, such as zinc finger nucleases (ZFNs), RNA interference (RNAi), or transcription activator-like effector nucleases (TALENs)^{18,19}. (RNAi) is activated via double-strand RNA (dsRNA), Originally found in *Caenorhabditis elegans*. After external dsRNA enters cells, it is converted to 21–23 base pairs of small interfering RNAs (siRNAs) via the RNase III family ribonuclease Dicer²⁰. Then, the RNA-induced silencing complex (RISC) is activated to the target RNA via siRNAs, ultimately destroying the gene silencing and target RNA. Nevertheless, the study of a particular gene by RNAi is restricted, as RNAi reduces gene expression through

transcription²¹.

Since its discovery in *Escherichia coli*, the CRISPR mechanism has been a dynamic immunity that protects against invasive foreign DNA²². Traditionally, CRISPR-Cas systems are divided into two classes based on six types. Class I (systems I, III, and IV) use different Cas proteins, whereas Class II (systems II, V, and VI) use the same Cas protein through various functions^{23, 24}. Thus, Class II CRISPR-Cas is more practical in bioengineering. Among the type II CRISPR Cas system, the most widely used in mammals is CRISPR-Cas9, produced by *Streptococcus pyogenes*²⁵.

3. The classical CRISPR/Cas9 mechanism

CRISPR/Cas9 is a genetically modified prokaryotic antiviral immune system attacking viral infections and utilizing RNA-guided nucleases to eliminate foreign DNA²⁶. This system comprises two parts, namely single-stranded guide RNA (sgRNA) and Cas9 endonuclease. The sgRNA serves as a Cas9 endonuclease, attacking the desired gene's DNA with a specific sequence²⁷. Consequently, the DNA cleaves at a series of three base pairs before the "NGG" protospacer adjacent motifs (PAM). CRISPR-Cas9 system makes genetic changes via small inserts or removals (indels) using the high-fidelity homology-directed repair or the relatively error-prone non-homologous end-joining^{28,29}.

4. Evolution of the CRISPR-Cas9 and other gene editing systems

In 1987, Japanese researchers found several unusual variants in the *E. coli* genome without examining their significance biologically. In 2002, they were named Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats (CRISPR), yet their value was unknown³⁰. In 2005, three study groups independently identified CRISPR loci in adaptive immunity, indicating protospacer-adjacent motifs (PAMs) might trigger the class II Cas9 nuclease to cut genomes³¹. CRISPR is responsible for innate immunity, and the sequence of phage genes inserted into bacteria can alter the bacteria's tolerance to phage³². The noncoding RNA derived from the CRISPR proto-interregional sequences directed Cas protein to the target region of the genome for defense.

Consequently, transcribing crRNA (tracrRNA) contributes to pre-crRNA maturation and new routes for crRNA maturation³³. Therefore, *in vitro* studies showed that maturing crRNA created a unique double-stranded RNA bond with tracrRNA via base pair, causing the Cas9 protein to induce double-strand breaks on the DNA mark. The type II Cas method cuts DNA in mammals, leading to CRISPR-Cas9 in gene editing. The Cas9 protein mutant dCas9 (endonuclease-deficient Cas9), without nuclease function, was first discovered³⁴. Later, CRISPR interference (CRISPRi) and the CRISPR activation tools were created by combining the dCas9 protein with transcription factors that stimulate or suppress DNA expression³⁵.

5. Chemical Modifications of CRISPR RNAs to Improve Gene-Editing Activity and Specificity

CRISPR has become a breakthrough method that can revolutionize medicine and biotechnology³⁶. Like other nucleic acid methods, CRISPR significantly benefits from chemical innovation to increase specificity and activity for crucial *in vivo* uses³⁷. Chemists have recently begun improving different elements of the CRISPR method; the following perspective is focused on chemical modifications of CRISPR RNAs (crRNAs). Early efforts concentrated on existing sugar and structure modifications (2'-deoxy, 2'-F, 2'-OMe, and phosphorothioates) as with other nucleic acid-based approaches³⁸. Some important changes in crRNAs have been made with bicyclic (locked) ribose and phosphate backbone replacements (phosphonoacetates and amides). However, chemical developments related to crRNAs are restricted to modifications used in antisense technologies and RNA interference³⁸. The positive results of these established modifications underscore the importance of chemists adopting a riskier approach. Further studies are required to investigate most effective chemical methods for advancing the development of CRISPR therapies and other *in vivo* techniques³⁸. CRISPR can provide the chance for chemists to combine advances in synthesis and molecular biochemistry for optimizing crRNA-protein interaction rationally.

6. DNA-based knockout-in Oncogenes

Unlike normal genes, oncogenes are controlled in different ways and can lead to cancerous transformations. The CRISPR/Cas9 system can interfere with the expression, deletion, or altering of oncogene activity, resulting in tumor inhibition³⁹. The CRISPR-Cas9-mediated deletion of CD-133 reduced vimentin's concentration in cancerous colon cells, especially decreased colony formation, and inhibited cell invasion and migration⁴⁰. The tumorigenic ability of Pancreatic cancer cells is significantly reduced by knocking down miR-3064 with CRISPR/Cas9⁴¹. Similarly, the growth of lung cancer cell lines H1650, A549, and H1975 was reduced with CRISPR-Cas9 deletions of oncogenic mutant EGFR alleles, with shrinking tumor sizes in mice treated using A549 or H1975 cells⁴². FAK gene knockdown with KRAS mutations in NSCLC cells using CRISPR/Cas9 caused noticeable DNA cleavage and improved radiotherapy sensitivity⁴³. Additionally, the CRISPR/Cas9-mediated removal of the E3 ubiquitin ligase UBR5 in an animal model of triple negative breast cancer (TNBC) greatly reduced the size of the tumor and *in vivo* invasion⁴⁴. This research showed that CRISPR/Cas9 gene editing could efficiently identify oncogenes and evaluate the medicinal potency of targeting oncogenes⁴⁴.

7. The delivery method of CRISPR Cas9 used in cancer studies

Several delivery methods can efficiently deliver CRISPR

parts into cells, including viral delivery methods and nonviral delivery methods.

7.1 Viral delivery system

Adenovirus and lentivirus frequently carry the plasmid CRISPR Cas9 method used to study tumors⁴⁵. The nonpathogenic adeno-associated virus can infect nondividing and dividing cells with low immunity. It was possible to successfully induce liver tumors by changing the Cre-expressing Cas9 mice liver⁴⁶. The researchers used the adenovirus to control the sgRNA library, achieving potential cancer suppressor DNA like Setd2, Trp53, and Pik3r1⁴⁷. With higher infection efficacy and lower immunogenicity, gene expression induced by lentivirus can last longer. After whole-genome CRISPR Cas9 monitoring using a lentiviral vector, a synthetic lethal factor via ATR inhibition *in vivo* and *in vitro* may cause RNASEH2 deficit⁴⁸. Nonetheless, the packaging ability of lentiviruses and adeno-associated viruses was low. Thus, the engineered expressing-Cas9 in mice, modified by adding sgRNA, was designed to defeat the encapsulation problem⁴⁹. A Cre-dependent Cas9 gene knockin mouse was designed by Platt et al. They utilized an AAV vector to add Lkb1, p53, and Kras-mutation to the lung, forming tumors⁵⁰. In contrast to lentiviruses and AAVs, adenoviruses have fewer sequence limitations and larger transgene sizes. The CRISPR part was similarly introduced to mouse tissue via tracheal recombinant adenovirus to cause Eml4-Alk gene interaction⁵¹, leading to lung tumorigenesis with increased penetration. As a result, low tissue orientation and high immunogenicity limit the adenovirus vectors' usage.

7.2. Nonviral delivery systems

Despite their low delivery rates, nonviral delivery techniques pose fewer health risks than virus vectors. Standard nonviral delivery methods include nanoparticles, electroporation, Hydrodynamic injection, and transposon carriers⁵². Chen et al. developed liposome-based hydrogel nanoparticles (LHNPs) using minicircle DNA engineering to carry a CRISPR-Cas9 mechanism against Plk1 (polo-like kinase 1), which effectively inhibited tumor growth⁵³. Another carrier to transfer guide RNA (gRNA) libraries for *in vivo* testing is piggyBac (PB) transposons, leading to conversion rates of 86.85-92.43% in mouse livers⁵⁴. Nonetheless, the nonviral delivery system do not often have sufficient level of tissue sensitivity and is overcome by Cas9 protein modification. Asialoglycoprotein receptor (ASGPr) is a c-type lectin that is expressed on the surface of liver cell⁵⁵. In another study, a Cas9 protein was created, carrying the ASGPr ligand and forming a combination with sgRNA to transfer the CRISPR-Cas9 part, specifically to liver cells⁵⁶.

8. Application of CRISPR -Cas9 in cancer

8.1. breast cancer

Cancer-related deaths among women are

disproportionately caused by breast cancer⁵⁷. CRISPR-Cas9 has been used to prevent various breast cancer types. Annunziato et al. created knockout mice in the cytosine base editor via conditional Cre expression⁵⁸. After direct delivery of the sgRNA encoding vector, efficient point mutations could be induced in one or more endogenous genes (Akt1, Pik3ca) by the CRISPR-Cas9 system. The system successfully influenced the cancer model (triple-negative breast cancer). In addition to the *in situ* development, organoid implantation of mice's breast cancer can imitate the development of breast tumor in humans. Dekkers et al. employed the CRISPR-Cas9 gene editing tool to target four different tumor suppressor genes (RB1, P53, PTEN, and NF1), related to breast cancer. The experiment was performed on breast progenitor cells from six different donors^{59,60}. The ER + intracellular tumors were created and long-term cultures were obtained after the 1/6 P53/PTEN/RB1 mutant cell line and 3/6 P53/PTEN/RB1/NF1 mutant cell line were transplanted into mice.

8.2. Lung cancer

Lung cancer is the primary cause of cancer deaths in humans worldwide⁶¹. The molecular and histopathological characteristics of lung tumors in humans can be induced in mice using chromosome rearrangement and CRISPR Cas9-mediated gene editing. Platt et al. employed the Cas9 system to introduce several sgRNAs into mice using an AAV vector. This resulted in the removal of mutations in lung p53 and Lkb1, as well as the homologous repair-induced Kras G12D mutation⁵⁰. In another study by Maddalo et al., virus-mediated CRISPR Cas9 was used to induce chromosomal rearrangement, resulting in the expression of the Eml4-Alk fusion gene. This approach was employed to create a mouse model of Eml4-Alk-driven lung cancer, which exhibited a responsive reaction to ALK-inhibitor therapy⁶².

9. Conclusion

Cancer is an intense danger to humans and needs a useful method to define its complicated genetic basis as a hereditary disease marked by cancerous cell proliferation. The CRISPR Cas9 gene editing science can be applied widely to cancer research to develop practical therapies and enhance research. In addition to off-target effects and immune reactions, moral considerations are also of concern in this method, which has long been disputed. Although the CRISPR-Cas9 gene editing technique may have certain limitations, it is widely acknowledged that this technology has the potential to significantly improve cancer treatment, despite its limitations.

Declarations

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Authors' contribution

Conceptualization: [Hassan Borji], ...; Methodology: [Soheil Sadr], ...; Formal analysis and investigation: [Pouria Ahmadi Simab/ Soheil Sadr], ...; Writing - original draft preparation: [All Authors]; Writing - review and editing: [Pouria Ahmadi Simab/Soheil]. All authors checked and approved the final version of the manuscript for publication in the present journal.

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Ethical considerations

Ethical issues (including plagiarism, consent to publish, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication and/or submission, and redundancy) have been checked by all the authors.

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